

In-vitro and In-vivo Characterization of Silver Nanoparticles for the Treatment of Lung Cancer

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Abstract:

Lung cancer remains a leading cause of cancer-related mortality worldwide, underscoring the need for innovative therapeutic strategies. This study explores the development and evaluation of silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) synthesized under optimized heating and cooling protocols to refine their physicochemical properties for antitumor applications. The AgNPs were synthesized using chemical synthesis using a reduction and bottom-up strategy. Eight synthesis protocols were optimized, and key parameters, such as particle size, morphology, and stability, were systematically characterized using UV–visible spectroscopy, dynamic light scattering, nanoparticle tracking analysis, and electron microscopy. Selected nanoparticles were evaluated for their cytotoxic effects on A549 lung adenocarcinoma cells, demonstrating dose- and time-dependent reductions in cell viability. Mechanistic insights revealed early apoptosis, assessed using flow cytometry by detecting phosphatidylserine externalization with Annexin V staining, propidium iodide uptake for membrane integrity, and lactate dehydrogenase release for cell damage. Surface coatings played a pivotal role, with citrate-stabilized AgNPs exhibiting rapid cytotoxicity and PVA-stabilized AgNPs showing sustained effects. This study underscores the importance of tailoring synthesis conditions to achieve reproducible and biologically effective AgNPs, providing a foundation for advancing nanotechnology-based cancer therapies.

Keywords: Silver nanoparticles; Chemical reduction; Surface stabilization; Lung cancer; Anti-tumor activity

1. Introduction

Lung cancer remains one of the leading causes of cancer-related mortality worldwide, with a high incidence and lethality. According to the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC), approximately 2.48 million new cases of lung cancer were reported in 2020, resulting in 1.82 million deaths [1]. Despite the availability of conventional therapies such as surgery, chemotherapy, and radiotherapy, these approaches often face limitations, including severe side effects and tumor resistance, creating a critical need for alternative therapeutic strategies [2]. Among emerging technologies, nanotechnology provides significant opportunities for cancer treatment. Silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) have gained attention due to their ability to induce oxidative stress, disrupt DNA, and promote apoptosis in cancer cells, making them strong candidates for biomedical applications [3]. However, the potential of AgNPs depends significantly on their synthesis, as their physicochemical properties—such as particle size, shape, and colloidal stability directly influence their interactions with tumor cells and subsequent biological responses [4]. Several methods have been employed to synthesize AgNPs, including chemical, physical, and biological approaches. Chemical synthesis, commonly performed by reduction processes, allows precise control over particle size and shape, making it a widely used. Physical methods, such as laser ablation or evaporation-condensation, also offer control over nanoparticle characteristics, but they generally require more complex and expensive equipment. Biological methods, utilizing plant extracts, microorganisms, or enzymes, provide a more eco-friendly alternative, although they can be less consistent and slower than chemical methods [5]. Each method presents advantages and limitations, such as scalability, cost, and reproducibility of nanoparticle characteristics, which are critical for biomedical applications. However, despite the variety of methods, there is no uniformity in the synthesis protocols that ensure the best reproducibility of the desired properties, which contributes to inconsistencies in biological outcomes and undermines the reliability of studies. One of the significant challenges in AgNP research is the lack of standardized protocols to ensure reproducibility and consistency in nanoparticle properties [6]. Variability in synthesis processes often leads to discrepancies in biological outcomes, compromising safety and efficacy. Defining robust criteria for nanoparticle characterization and synthesis acceptance is essential to address this. These criteria must encompass key

physicochemical attributes, such as uniform particle size, controlled surface charge, and stability, ensuring that only AgNPs with favorable properties proceed to biological evaluation. This study established a set of rigorous eligibility criteria to assess the suitability of various AgNPs synthesis protocols [7]. The criteria included straightforward visual inspections, such as color change and turbidity, and advanced analytical techniques, including UV-visible spectroscopy, dynamic light scattering (DLS), and electron microscopy. Suboptimal methods were rapidly identified and excluded by systematically evaluating synthesis protocols against these benchmarks, streamlining the selection of reproducible and effective AgNPs formulations. The A549 lung adenocarcinoma cell line was chosen for biological evaluation due to its established relevance in nanotoxicology and its representation of a tumor microenvironment [8]. This cell line provides a robust model for assessing the cytotoxic effects of AgNPs, with well-documented responses to nanoparticle exposure. AgNPs are widely recognized for their cytotoxic effects, primarily through oxidative stress induction silver ion release, direct interactions with cellular organelles, such as mitochondria, and macromolecules, such as DNA [9]. These pathways lead to apoptosis, highlighting the importance of evaluating early apoptotic events and membrane integrity. This distinction is crucial in nanotoxicology to differentiate apoptosis from necrosis, ensuring precise identification of the affected cell populations and a better understanding of nanoparticle-induced cytotoxicity [10]. Evaluating colloidal stability and toxicity is crucial to ensure the safe use of AgNPs in biomedical applications. These assessments help determine the nanoparticles' suitability for biomedical applications. Cell viability assays, including MTT and LDH assays, indicated a dose-dependent cytotoxic effect, with PVA-stabilized AgNPs displaying a more gradual silver ion release and reduced toxicity compared to citrate-stabilized AgNPs. These differences are attributed to forming a protective layer around the nanoparticles, modulating their cellular interactions AgNPs were selected for this study due to their well-established antitumor activity and ability to induce selective cytotoxicity in cancer cells. Previous studies have demonstrated that AgNPs can induce apoptosis without significantly affecting normal cells [11]. Furthermore, their biological activity can be modulated through different coatings, allowing for optimization of therapeutic effects while minimizing systemic toxicity. Additionally, the literature presents a diverse range of synthesis protocols for AgNPs, leading to inconsistencies in physicochemical properties and biological effects. Therefore, optimizing and standardizing these protocols for precise tumor evaluation is an urgent need, ensuring reproducibility and reliability in nanomedicine applications [12].

2. Materials and methods

Synthesis of AgNPs

AgNPs were synthesized using two distinct synthesis approaches: a heating method, which involved thermal reduction with PVA as a stabilizing agent at 90 °C, and a cooling method, where chemical reduction was performed at room temperature with TSC as the stabilizer. Both synthesis methods are based on the chemical reduction approach and follow the bottom-up strategy. Each approach was refined with optimized parameters, resulting in eight distinct variations. The optimized heating and cooling protocols were adapted from previously established methodologies by Agnihotri et al. and Melo et al. respectively. These optimized protocols aim to enhance the reproducibility and consistency of the synthesis process. As part of the bottom-up strategy, the chemical reduction approach allows for enhanced control over particle size and shape, offering advantages such as uniformity and reproducibility of AgNPs characteristics [13, 14].

Optimized heating protocol for AgNPs synthesis

AgNPs were synthesized via a heating reduction method using highpurity reagents: sodium borohydride (NaBH_4 , $\geq 98\%$), trisodium citrate (TSC, $\geq 99\%$), and silver nitrate (AgNO_3 , $\geq 99\%$) obtained from SigmaAldrich. Ultrapure Milli-Q water was used throughout the synthesis to minimize contamination. The glassware used in the process was cleaned meticulously with acid and neutral detergent and autoclaved at 121 °C for 20 min to eliminate any residual impurities. For the optimized heating protocol, 48 mL of Milli-Q water was combined with NaBH_4 (1.0×10^{-3} mol/L) and TSC (1.06×10^{-3} mol/L) and heated to 60 °C under vigorous stirring, protected from light. After 30 min, 2 mL of an AgNO_3 solution (1.0×10^{-3} mol/L) was added dropwise, followed by heating to 90 °C for 20 min. A color change from transparent to yellow indicated AgNPs formation. The suspension was centrifuged at $12,000 \times g$ for 15 min to separate the nanoparticles, which were then resuspended in MilliQ water and stored at 4 °C.

Optimized cooling protocol for AgNPs synthesis

The optimized cooling protocol followed a similar approach, with pre-chilled reagents to control reaction kinetics. Sodium borohydride (2.0×10^{-3} mol/L) was prepared in 75 mL of Milli-Q water and cooled to 0 °C in an ice bath for 10–15 min. While stirring continuously, 25 mL of AgNO_3 solution (1.0×10^{-3} mol/L) was added dropwise using a Pasteur pipette. Polyvinyl alcohol (PVA, $\geq 99\%$) at 0.3% was introduced as a stabilizer to enhance colloidal stability. The synthesized nanoparticles were centrifuged, resuspended in Milli-Q water, and stored at 4 °C for further use.

Refinement and optimization of protocols for AgNPs synthesis

Both protocols were refined with adjustments to reaction parameters, including reagent concentrations, dropwise addition rates, reaction times, and intermediate solution usage to improve the reproducibility and quality of AgNP. Acid-cleaning of glassware and adjustments to stirring times were particularly effective in reducing nanoparticle heterogeneity. Increased reaction volumes and the immediate addition of stabilizers after color change also contributed to enhanced stability and repeatability. Modifications were implemented to address the inconsistencies observed in Protocols 1 and 2 and optimize the synthesis process, resulting in three additional protocols for each synthesis category. These were designated as Protocols 1.1, 1.2, and 1.3 for the heating category and Protocols 2.1, 2.2, and 2.3 for the cooling category. The modifications included adjustments to key parameters, such as reagent concentrations, cleaning methods for glassware, rate of dropwise reagent addition, use of stabilizers, pH adjustment, reagent batch variations, reaction time, and inclusion of intermediate solutions.

Eligibility criteria for AgNPs after synthesis

The specific eligibility criteria were established, comprising inclusion and characterization criteria to identify the batches of AgNPs with the highest antitumor potential. These criteria aligned with the study's objectives and facilitated the systematic evaluation of synthesis protocols.

Characterization of AgNPs

Ultraviolet-Visible (UV–Visible) absorption spectroscopy

The formation of AgNPs was confirmed using UV-visible spectroscopy (Molecular Devices SpectraMax 190), measuring absorbance across 200–800 nm at a resolution of 2 nm. Characteristic plasmon resonance peaks at approximately 400 nm confirmed AgNPs formation. High absorbance intensity suggested adequate nanoparticle concentration, while narrow peak widths indicated uniform particle sizes.

Dynamic light scattering (DLS)

Particle size distribution, polydispersity index (PDI), and zeta potential were analyzed using a Zetasizer Nano ZS (Malvern Instruments). Measurements were performed in ultrapure Milli-Q water and three culture media DMEM Low Glucose, DMEM High Glucose, and RPMI- 1640 (Sigma-Aldrich) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS, Gibco™). DLS measurements were performed at 25 °C using 10 mm polystyrene disposable cuvettes.

Nanoparticle tracking analysis (NTA)

NTA analysis was performed to determine the concentration (number of particles/mL) and size distribution of the AgNPs. The ZetaView system (Particle Metrix, Germany) was calibrated with 100 nm polystyrene nanoparticles (Microtrac GmbH) prior to measurements. The AgNP samples were diluted 100-fold in distilled water and injected into the sample chamber (1 mL) using a sterile syringe (SR). Measurements were carried out within the optimal dilution range ($9 \times 10^7 - 2.9 \times 10^9$ particles/mL) using ZetaView software (Particle Metrix GmbH) at 25 °C.

X-ray diffraction (XRD)

The AgNPs powder precipitate was placed on 10 mm nylon holders ("loop" Hampton Research, USA) and subjected to powder diffraction analysis using a SuperNova diffractometer (Rigaku, USA). The analysis was performed at room temperature, operating at 40 W (50 kV and 0.8 mA) with CuK α radiation (1.5416 Å) and phi-scan rotation. Data were collected in the 20° to 90° (2 θ) range and processed using the CrysAlisPro® software (Agilent).

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM)

To analyze particle size and shape, 5 μ L of the AgNPs solution in ultrapure water were deposited onto copper grids (200 mesh) coated with Formvar and dried in a vacuum desiccator. Micrographs were obtained using a Tecnai Spirit G2 TEM (FEI, USA) operating at 80 kV, with 500 particles analyzed for each batch. The images were processed using ImageJ software to estimate the diameter and circularity of the AgNPs.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS)

The elemental composition was determined by Energy-Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (EDS) using a Quanta FEG 450 Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) (FEI Company, Hillsboro, Oregon, USA), operating at 5 kV. The AgNP samples in water were dried in Eppendorf tubes using a Speedvac Vacufuge Plus (Eppendorf, Hamburg, Germany) overnight. The resulting precipitate was deposited on SEM stubs coated with double-sided carbon tape for analysis.

Evaluation of antitumoral effects

Cell culture

Here, we used the human lung carcinoma cell line A549 (ATCC CCL- 185™), supplied by the Cell Bank of Rio de Janeiro (BCRJ, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil), packed in frozen ampoules and kept in liquid nitrogen after purchasing from American Type Culture Collection (ATCC). The A549 cells were cultured in Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Medium (DMEM) High Glucose (Sigma-Aldrich), supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS, Gibco™). The cultures were maintained under standard conditions in a humidified incubator at 37 °C with 5% CO₂. Tests for bacteria, fungi, and mycoplasmas ensured sterility. For bacteria and fungi, the cell culture supernatant was placed in thioglycolate (TIO) (Acumedia, Baltimore, USA) and tryptic soy broth (TSB) and incubated aerobically for 14 days at 22.5 ± 2.5 °C and 32.5 ± 2.5 °C, respectively. Mycoplasma contamination in the cell supernatants was investigated by bioluminescence using the MycoAlert™ PLUS Mycoplasma Detection Kit

Cell viability assay by MTT reduction

Cells were seeded in 96-well plates (Millicell® EZ) at a density of 7×10^3 cells/well and exposed to varying concentrations of AgNPs (10, 25, 50, 75, and 100 µg/mL) for 24, 48, and 72 h. The culture medium used was DMEM High Glucose, supplemented with 10% FBS. MTT (3-(4,5- dimethylthiazol-2-yl)- 2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide) was added to each well at a final 1.0 mg/mL concentration. Triton™ X-100 at 0.1% was included as a positive control (C+) to induce cell death. After a three-hour incubation at 37 °C in a humidified atmosphere with 5% CO₂, the supernatant was carefully removed, and the resulting formazan crystals were dissolved in 100 µL of isopropanol. The absorbance of the dissolved formazan was measured at 570 nm using a Synergy™ HTX microplate reader. This absorbance reflects the metabolic activity of the cells, providing an indirect measurement of cell viability.

Cell viability assay by lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) activity

LDH activity was quantified using the CyQuant LDH colorimetric kit (Invitrogen). The A549 cells were cultured in 96-well plates (7×10^3 cells/well) and treated with AgNPs (10–100 µg/mL) for 24, 48, and 72 h. After treatment, 10 µL of cell lysis buffer was added for maximum LDH release, while 10 µL of Milli-Q water was used as a spontaneous release control. The samples were incubated at 37 °C for 45

min, and then the LDH substrate was added and incubated for 30 min at room temperature, protected from light. Absorbance was measured at 490 nm using a Synergy™ HTX microplate reader.

Real-Time cell proliferation monitoring by electrical impedance

The A549 cells were seeded in 96-well plates of the E-Plate View xCELLigence RTCA SP type at a density of 7×10^3 cells per well. The plates, equipped with gold microelectrodes on the bottom surface, were calibrated with the culture medium and adjusted to an electric potential of 22 mV. The system monitored the electrical impedance of the cells in real time, recording data every hour for 96 h. After cell adhesion (24 h), the cells were treated with different concentrations of AgNPs (10, 25, 50, 75, and 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$), and the treatment was maintained for 72 h. Impedance was used to calculate the Cell Index (CI) using the formula: $\text{CI} = (\text{Impedance at a given time} - \text{Impedance in the absence of cells}) / \text{Nominal impedance value}$.

Cell death assay by Annexin V/PI staining

Cell death by apoptosis or necrosis was assessed by flow cytometry. A549 cells were cultured in 75 cm² flasks (7×10^3 cells per well) and treated with AgNPs (10, 25, 50, 75, and 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) for 72 h. On the analysis day, cells were trypsinized, centrifuged, and counted in a Neubauer chamber. A total of 2×10^5 cells was used for each experimental condition. The cells were washed, resuspended in 1x Annexin V buffer, and stained with 5 μL of Alexa Fluor™ 488 Annexin V and 1 μL of Propidium Iodide (PI). After incubation on ice for 15 min, the samples were diluted in 400 μL of binding buffer and analyzed by flow cytometry (BD FACSAria™ III), recording 20,000 events per condition.

Statistical analysis

The data from the AgNPs characterization were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation. The results were presented as the mean optical density (O.D.) \pm standard deviation in the cell viability assays, with readings taken at 570 nm for the MTT assay and 490 nm for the LDH assay. Statistical analysis was performed using GraphPad Prism software, applying the unpaired *t*-test and one-way ANOVA, followed by Tukey or Dunnett multiple comparison tests to compare the treated groups with the control group. FlowJo software was used to analyze flow cytometry data. Statistical significance was defined as $p < 0.05$; $*p < 0.01$; and $**p < 0.001$.

3. Results

Synthesis and characterization of AgNPs

Selection of batches of AgNPs after synthesis

The synthesis of AgNPs using different protocols yielded eight distinct batches: four from the heating and cooling categories. Each batch was photographed immediately after synthesis to document its visual characteristics. The batches were subjected to eligibility criteria, including color, turbidity, and UV-visible spectroscopy, to evaluate their suitability. All batches exhibited the characteristic color change indicative of AgNPs formation (Fig. 1a), with colors ranging from yellow and orange hues (batches 01, 02, 03, 04) to brown (batch 06) and coppery tones (batches 07 and 08). Despite these variations, batches 03, 04, 07, and 08 were excluded due to unacceptable coloration and turbidity. UV-visible spectroscopic analysis (Fig. 1b) revealed single absorbance peaks above 1.5 AU at 400 nm with narrow plasmonic bandwidths, suggesting the presence of small, spherical nanoparticles. However, batches 01 and 03 failed to meet this criterion, showing peaks below 1.5 AU and broader plasmonic curves. Batches 02 and 05 successfully met all eligibility criteria and were selected for subsequent characterization experiments. In contrast, batch 06 was excluded due to significant instability, which became evident over time. Despite initially meeting the criteria, it displayed pronounced changes in color and spectral properties, ultimately resulting in precipitation after five months (Fig. 1c).

Fig. 1. (a) Synthesis of AgNPs: Different synthesis protocols resulted in eight lots, four from the heating class (01, 02, 03, 04) and four from the cooling class (05, 06, 07, 08). (b) UV–Visible spectra: Plasmonic bands for each lot are displayed. (c) Spectral changes and precipitation in Lot 06: Spectral modifications and visible precipitation observed in the absence of stabilizer (PVA). Results represent three independent experiments.

Fig. 2. (a) Size and PDI of AgNPs in ultrapure water and culture media (10% FBS): Lot 02 exhibited an average diameter of 25.77 ± 0.08 nm (PDI: 0.485 ± 0.001) in water, while Lot 05 exhibited 28.7 ± 1.18 nm (PDI: 0.497 ± 0.026). In culture media, Lot 02 had diameters of 28.08 ± 0.44 nm in DMEM Low, 28.69 ± 0.60 nm in DMEM High, and 42.53 ± 9.34 nm in RPMI, with respective PDIs of 0.460 ± 0.006 , 0.564 ± 0.07 , and 0.454 ± 0.13 . Lot 05 exhibited 35.22 ± 0.06 nm in DMEM Low, 34.74 ± 0.03 nm in DMEM High, and 36.78 ± 0.03 nm in RPMI, with PDIs of 0.497 ± 0.06 , 0.481 ± 0.03 , and 0.453 ± 0.03 . (b) Population size distribution for Lot 02 in water and culture media: Predominant diameters of 28.57 nm in water, 38.34 nm in DMEM Low, 37.69 nm in DMEM High, and 56.33 nm in RPMI. (c) Population size distribution for Lot 05 in water and culture media: Predominant diameters of 39.82 nm in water, 38.84 nm in DMEM Low, 37.84 nm in DMEM High, and 38.73 nm in RPMI. (d) Zeta potential (ZP) of Lots 02 and 05: Stability was observed in water, while higher instability was noted in culture media. (e–f) Population distribution and concentration: Lot 02 had 90.7% of its population with a diameter of 35.8 nm and a concentration of 2.69×10^9 particles/mL. Lot 05 had 85.6% with 45.1 nm and 2.19×10^9 particles/mL. Data are mean \pm SD from three independent experiments ($n = 3$).

Fig. 3. (a) EDX chemical composition of Lot 02: Presence of Silver, Oxygen, Sodium, and Carbon. (b) EDX chemical composition of Lot 05: Presence of Silver, Oxygen, Sodium and Carbon. (c–d) XRD diffractograms: Peaks at 2θ values of 38° , 44° , 64° , and 77° , corresponding to reflection planes (111), (200), (220), and (311) of AgNP crystal structures.

Fig. 4. (a,b) Size distribution for Lot 02: 99.8% of the population had diameters ranging from 8 to 42 nm, with only 0.2% at 42 nm. (c) Circularity analysis of Lot 02: 17% of the population exhibited perfect symmetry (1.0), with 24.5% ranging between 0.8 and 0.95. (d,e) Size distribution for Lot 05: 73.03% of the population had diameters between 5 and 40 nm, while 26.97% ranged from 45 to 85 nm. (f) Circularity analysis of Lot 05: 50% exhibited perfect circularity (1.0), with 24% ranging between 0.8 and 0.95.

In vitro antitumor assays

Cytotoxicity analysis by MTT assay in A549 cells

The viability of A549 cells exposed to both batches 02 and 05 was assessed using the MTT assay. The analysis was conducted at 24, 48, and 72 h post-treatment to evaluate the impact of AgNPs on mitochondrial activity. After 24 h (Fig. 5a), batch 02 showed a reduction in mitochondrial activity at concentrations of 75 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ ($87 \% \pm 3.2$) and 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ ($79 \% \pm 4.1$). Batch 05, however, exhibited a reduction only at the 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ concentration ($87 \% \pm 2.8$). After 48 h (Fig. 5b), both batches continuously declined mitochondrial activity. Batch 02 showed reduced activity at concentrations of 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ ($87 \% \pm 5.5$), 75 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ ($78 \% \pm 4.4$), and 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ ($58 \% \pm 2.3$). Batch 05 showed a reduction at 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ ($65 \% \pm 3.7$). After 72 h (Fig. 5c), the reduction in mitochondrial activity persisted for both batches at the same concentrations. For batch 02, the values were 75 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ ($75 \% \pm 2.2$) and 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ ($15 \% \pm 4.5$), while for batch 05, the values were 75 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ ($77 \% \pm 5.1$) and 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ ($18 \% \pm 1.2$).

LDH release assay for cell membrane integrity evaluation

The LDH colorimetric assay assessed cell membrane integrity following exposure for both batches (02 and 05) at 24, 48, and 72 h. The results showed no significant increase in LDH levels at the tested concentrations compared to the positive control (C+), which exhibited high LDH release (Fig. 6). The absence of LDH leakage into the extracellular medium suggests that cell death occurred primarily through apoptosis rather than necrosis at all-time points.

Evaluation of cell death by flow cytometry

Cell death was evaluated by flow cytometry using the Live/Dead assay, which allowed the analysis of necrotic and apoptotic populations (both early and late) after exposure to AgNPs from batches 02 and 05. The cells were treated with 75 and 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ concentrations for 72 h, and the results indicated a reduction in cell viability and an increase in cell death (Fig. 7). For batch 02, $14 \pm 1.13\%$ of the cells remained viable at 75 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, and $18 \pm 4\%$ were viable at 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$. Apoptosis was the predominant form of cell death, with $83 \pm 1\%$ of cells in early apoptosis and $2 \pm 0.2\%$ in late apoptosis at 75 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$. At 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, $79 \pm 3\%$ were in early apoptosis and $2 \pm 1\%$ in late apoptosis. For batch 05, $17 \pm 0.5\%$ of the cells remained viable at 75 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, with $80 \pm 0.5\%$ in early apoptosis and $2.6 \pm 1\%$ in late

apoptosis. At 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ of AgNPs, $21 \pm 2.3\%$ were viable, $77 \pm 2.4\%$ were in early apoptosis, and $2.5 \pm 0.1\%$ were in late apoptosis. Neither batch exhibited significant necrosis at the tested concentrations. For batch 02, necrosis was $0.021 \pm 0.009\%$ at 75 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ and $0.021 \pm 0.005\%$ at 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$. For batch 05, the necrosis values were $0.012 \pm 0.005\%$ and $0.014 \pm 0.01\%$, respectively (Fig. 7).

Real-Time cellular monitoring by electrical impedance

Fig. 8 illustrates the proliferation analysis of A549 cells based on cellular index (CI) values obtained using electrical impedance in the xCELLigence device. A549 cells were treated with various concentrations of AgNPs (10, 25, 50, 75, and 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) for 72 h. No significant differences in CI were observed after 72 h of exposure to the AgNPs, and neither batch of AgNPs caused any changes in cellular proliferation over time. In contrast, a decrease in CI was observed in the positive control (C+) for cell death (cells treated with Triton™ X-100 0.1%), while an exponential increase in CI over time was noted in the negative control (C-) (DMEM High 10% FBS, used as the control for viable cells without nanoparticles).

Fig.5. A549 cell viability by MTT: MTT reduction assay performed on A549 cells exposed to AgNPs at concentrations of 10, 25, 50, 75, and 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ at 24 h (a), 48 h (b), and 72 h (c). Both lots of AgNPs reduced cell viability and mitochondrial metabolism after 48 h of treatment at 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$. The DMEM (high) condition represents the negative control (viable cells), while cell death control was performed with Triton™ X-100 0.1%. Three independent experiments were conducted. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA with

multiple comparisons by Dunnett compared to the respective control group (C-) ($* p < 0.05$; $** p < 0.01$; $*** p < 0.001$).

Fig. 6. A549 cell viability by LDH: LDH release assay conducted on A549 cells exposed to AgNPs at concentrations of 10, 25, 50, 75, and 100 µg/mL at 24 h (a,b,c) and 72 h (d,e,f). No significant LDH leakage was observed in Lot 02 (a,b,c) and Lot 05 (d,e,f), suggesting possible apoptosis. The C+ condition represents maximum LDH release (positive control). Three independent experiments were conducted. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA with multiple comparisons by Dunnett compared to the respective control group (C+) ($* p < 0.05$; $** p < 0.01$; $*** p < 0.001$). (Note: ns – not significant).

4. Discussion

Lung cancer remains a leading cause of cancer-related mortality worldwide, emphasizing the need for innovative therapeutic approaches to improve patient outcomes. AgNPs have garnered attention due to their unique physicochemical properties and ability to induce cytotoxic effects on tumor cells. However, challenges such as controlling nanoparticle size, stability, and biological interactions have hindered their translational potential. This study addressed these challenges by establishing rigorous inclusion and eligibility criteria to evaluate the acceptability of AgNP batches for subsequent biological analyses, ensuring reproducibility and stability in both aqueous and biological media [15-17]. Furthermore, the antitumor activity of these nanoparticles was systematically assessed against A549 cells. However, while the A549 cell line is typically cultured in DMEM High, additional media such as DMEM Low and RPMI were included to broaden the analysis of colloidal stability and nanoparticle behavior under varying biological conditions. In contrast to previous studies that focused on single media types, this

approach provided a more comprehensive assessment of nanoparticle performance. By integrating detailed physicochemical characterization with biological assays, this study demonstrated the efficacy of AgNPs as antitumor agents.

A key strength of this work was the application of recognized guidelines and standards, including NIST 1200–29, ISO 19,337:2023, and ISO 22,412:2017 [18-20], during the synthesis and characterization of AgNPs. These frameworks were adapted to meet the study's objectives, ensuring methodological rigor, reliable comparisons, and reproducibility. This adherence to standardized approaches differentiates this study from others, where variability in synthesis and characterization protocols often undermines the reliability of findings. AgNPs were chemically synthesized by reduction, comprehensively characterized, and evaluated for their antitumor potential against the A549 lung cancer cell line. Batches 02 and 05 were selected based on rigorously predefined criteria, including optical characteristics, colloidal stability, and favorable physicochemical properties, essential for maintaining consistency in biological assays. The formation of AgNPs was confirmed through observable color changes in the solutions, transitioning to yellow-orange tones due to the Localized Surface Plasmon Resonance (LSPR) effect. This phenomenon, characteristic of noble metals in colloidal form, occurs when light interacts with surface electrons of nanoparticles, generating oscillations that result in specific light absorption [21-23]. The LSPR effect is a critical indicator of nanoparticle formation and is extensively studied for its correlation with size and shape distributions. Analysis of the synthesized batches revealed consistent LSPR effects across all samples, with color variations ranging from yellow-orange to darker shades, such as brown and copper. Notably, these color variations, including darker brown tones in some nanoparticles, do not necessarily disqualify them from biomedical applications. The suitability of nanoparticles for biomedical use is not determined by color alone but rather by a combination of factors such as particle size, shape, aggregation state, colloidal stability, and biological efficacy [24]. These variations reflect nanoparticle homogeneity and size distribution differences, which directly influence their optical properties, biological stability, and cytotoxic potential. Although darker color tones may indicate changes in these properties, they should be evaluated alongside other critical parameters, including colloidal stability and size distribution. Therefore, while color can serve as a useful preliminary indicator, it must be complemented by comprehensive physicochemical and biological analyses to accurately assess the biomedical applicability of the nanoparticles. In contrast to other studies using commercial nanoparticles or alternative synthesis routes where visual coloration is often overlooked this work integrated color analysis with LSPR-UV profiles in the visible spectrum, offering

a more comprehensive assessment of the homogeneity and colloidal stability of AgNPs. While some studies have relied solely on UV–Vis analysis without considering visual coloration, this omission can limit the interpretation of optical and colloidal behavior. By combining visual assessments with spectral analysis, we achieved a more robust characterization of the nanoparticles' physical and chemical properties. Building on this comprehensive approach, the synthesis methods employed in this study followed a bottom-up strategy, widely recognized for their ability to produce nanoparticles with controlled size and morphology [25]. This method promotes the formation of highly defined structures from individual atoms or molecules, ensuring uniformity and reproducibility key factors for reliable biological evaluations. Integrating visual and spectral analyses with a controlled bottom-up synthesis process was crucial for enhancing the reproducibility of nanoparticle properties, which directly influences their biological performance [26]. These findings align with broader literature emphasizing the importance of precise control over synthesis parameters to ensure reproducibility and optimize nanoparticle properties. For instance, Facibeni et al. (2023) demonstrated that fine-tuning synthesis conditions, such as reagent concentrations and stabilizer choice, significantly impact nanoparticle size, uniformity, and biological efficacy. Similarly, Duman et al. (2024) [27] highlighted that optimizing synthesis protocols enhances reproducibility and performance, while inconsistencies in size and shape often result in variability in biological responses and optical behaviors. The observed color variations and LSPR profiles in this study validated the successful formation of AgNPs and emphasized the need for rigorous characterization and methodological precision [28]. Shifts in the LSPR absorption peak from the typical ~ 400 nm do not inherently disqualify AgNPs from biomedical applications. Instead, these shifts may arise from particle size, shape, or surface functionalization changes—factors that can be optimized to maintain or enhance biological efficacy. Integrating visual assessments with spectral analysis ensured a more robust characterization of the nanoparticles' physical and chemical properties. As highlighted in recent studies, these combined approaches are crucial for improving reproducibility and advancing the translational potential of AgNP-based applications, particularly in biomedical contexts. This comprehensive characterization was essential for selecting appropriate stabilizers, such as PVA and TSC, to enhance nanoparticle stability and performance in biological environments.

Fig.7. Cell death by Annexin V/PI after 72 h exposure to AgNPs: Flow cytometry analysis of cell viability using the Annexin V/PI kit showing predominantly early and late apoptosis after A549 cells were exposed to AgNPs at concentrations of 75 and 100 µg/mL for 72h. Cells negative for both Annexin V and PI markers (Annexin V-/PI-) represent live cells, while those positive for Annexin V (Annexin V+/PI-) are undergoing early apoptosis, and those positive for both markers (Annexin V+/ PI+) are undergoing late apoptosis.

Fig.8. Proliferation of A549 cells after 24 h, 48 h, and 72 h after treatment with AgNPs by electrical impedance: AgNPs from both batches did not cause changes in cell adhesion and proliferation at the different concentrations used (10; 25; 50; 75 and 100 µg/mL). The experiment was carried out for 96 h; after 24 h, the cells were treated

with AgNPs for a subsequent exposure period of 72h. Three independent experiments were completed. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA with Dunnett's multiple comparisons in comparison to the specific control group (C-) (* $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$). (Note: ns – not significant).

These stabilizers formed self-assembled protective layers around the nanoparticles, minimizing aggregation a critical factor for applications in biological systems. Concerns regarding the potential cytotoxicity of these stabilizers were addressed by referencing extensive literature demonstrating that sodium citrate and PVA, at the concentrations used, pose no significant toxic risks. Both compounds are widely recognized for their safety in biomedical applications [29]. Additionally, solution turbidity served as a quality control criterion, with more translucent solutions indicating higher synthesis accuracy and fewer impurities. synthesized uncoated AgNPs, resulting in particle sizes exceeding 100 nm in water and even larger in culture media, indicating reduced colloidal stability. These findings underscore the importance of stabilizers in AgNP synthesis to maintain nanometric size under varying biological conditions and to ensure consistency and enhanced performance in biomedical applications. Together, these stabilization strategies and rigorous synthesis monitoring highlight the meticulous approach required to produce AgNPs with reliable and reproducible properties for biomedical use. In addition to stabilizers, pH played a crucial role in maintaining the colloidal stability and biological performance of the synthesized AgNPs. The pH values measured were 6.57 ± 1.2 for the optimized heating protocol and 7.4 ± 0.4 for the optimized cooling protocol, both near neutrality. These conditions are optimal for preserving nanoparticle stability and preventing aggregation factors essential for consistent biological interactions. Furthermore, neutral to slightly acidic pH levels help minimize excessive silver ion release, thereby reducing potential cytotoxic effects and enhancing biocompatibility in biological environments. The synthesis temperature 90 °C for the heating protocol was chosen to ensure complete reduction reactions and precise nanoparticle size and shape control. Elevated temperatures accelerate the reduction process and promote uniform nucleation, producing more homogeneous particles. Although lower temperatures can also be effective, as the cooling protocol demonstrates, higher temperatures enhance reaction efficiency and colloidal stability [30]. This dual-temperature approach offers flexibility in synthesis, optimizing the balance between particle uniformity and process efficiency. Among the synthesized batches, only batches 02 and 05 met all the predefined inclusion criteria, qualifying them for further physicochemical characterization. Batch 06, although initially meeting some criteria, such as an acceptable LSPR response, was excluded due to pronounced changes in color and spectral properties over time, resulting in precipitation. Similarly, batches 03, 04, 07, and 08 were disqualified due to unacceptable coloration and turbidity, while batches 01 and 03 exhibited substantial spectral variations

in peak width and intensity, reinforcing their exclusion. Batch 05, stabilized with PVA, exhibited a more gradual cytotoxic effect, likely due to PVA acting as a physical barrier that delays the release of silver ions. This property makes PVA-coated AgNPs particularly relevant for controlled release applications, where a gradual ion release is desirable to minimize immediate toxic effects and extend therapeutic activity. Although this study shares similarities with the works of BLANCO et al. (2017) and MATYSIAK-KUCHAREK et al. (2023), it introduces significant innovations. Unlike these studies, which used commercial nanoparticles, we developed customized chemical synthesis protocols based on reduction reactions, enabling precise control over the size, homogeneity, and colloidal stability of AgNPs. Additionally, we conducted a detailed analysis of nanoparticle behavior in various culture media, evaluating parameters such as zeta potential, polydispersity index, and hydrodynamic size. This approach allowed us to explore the interactions between synthesis conditions and colloidal stability in biological environments an aspect not addressed in previous studies limited to prefabricated particles. Another distinguishing feature of our work was the focus on targeted cytotoxicity, employing strategies to select the most effective nanoparticle batches for antitumor applications, ensuring greater reproducibility and enhanced biological performance. Moreover, we incorporated X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis to confirm the formation of metallic silver and the absence of oxides, an aspect not discussed in the aforementioned studies. These contributions emphasize the innovative character of this research in comparison to existing works. These innovations are particularly relevant for understanding the cytotoxic profiles observed, as evidenced by the annexin V/PI assays performed in this study. Based on the observed cytotoxic profiles, annexin V/PI assays provided further insights into the mode of cell death induced by AgNPs. Both batches predominantly triggered early apoptosis after 72 h of exposure at 75 and 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ concentrations. This finding aligns with existing evidence that apoptosis, rather than necrosis, is the primary mechanism of AgNP-induced cytotoxicity, reducing the risk of exacerbated inflammatory responses [31]. This study stresses the importance of detailed physicochemical characterization as a cornerstone for reproducibility in nanotoxicology, providing a robust foundation for correlating synthesis parameters with biological effects. Such reproducibility is essential for bridging the gap between preclinical studies and clinical applications, ensuring consistent and reliable therapeutic outcomes. While the promising in vitro results suggest potential, further in vivo studies are needed to confirm the translational potential of these nanoparticles. Future research should also explore the functionalization of AgNPs with tumor-targeting ligands to enhance selectivity and minimize off-target effects. Additionally, advanced analytical techniques, such as proteomics for corona profiling, could

deepen our understanding of nanoparticle-biomolecule interactions, facilitating the design of safer and more effective nanotherapeutics. Together, these strategies represent a significant step forward in nanomedicine, contributing to developing more reliable, targeted, and safer AgNP-based therapies for lung cancer [32].

5. Conclusion

This study highlights the importance of establishing rigorous eligibility criteria to assess the suitability of AgNP synthesis protocols. These criteria enabled the selection of nanoparticles with reproducible physicochemical properties including controlled size, morphology, and colloidal stability—making them suitable for antitumor applications. These standardized protocols identified batches 02 and 05 as optimal candidates, demonstrating dose- and time-dependent cytotoxic effects against A549 cells. Cell death predominantly occurred through early apoptosis, with citrate-stabilized AgNPs (batch 02) exhibiting rapid cytotoxicity and PVA-stabilized AgNPs (batch 05) showing sustained activity. Comprehensive physicochemical characterization confirmed the crystalline nature of the AgNPs. XRD analysis revealed characteristic silver peaks, while electron microscopy demonstrated a predominantly spherical morphology. Hydrodynamic size and zeta potential analyses highlighted stability variations across different culture media, with batch 02 showing increased aggregation in RPMI. NTA provided additional confirmation of particle size and concentration, reinforcing the reproducibility of the synthesis protocols. The pH of the synthesized solutions also played a critical role in maintaining nanoparticle stability and ensuring consistent biological interactions. The heating protocol had a slightly acidic pH of 6.57, while the cooling protocol maintained a neutral pH of 7.4. These pH conditions enhanced colloidal stability by minimizing aggregation and excessive silver ion release, improving biocompatibility and reducing potential cytotoxic effects in biological environments. Biological assays demonstrated significant reductions in cell viability in a dose- and time-dependent manner. MTT assays confirmed impairment of mitochondrial activity, while LDH assays indicated that membrane integrity was largely preserved, supporting apoptosis as the primary mode of cell death. Flow cytometry analysis further validated these findings, showing a predominance of early apoptotic cells following exposure to AgNPs. Additionally, real-time electrical impedance monitoring confirmed that AgNPs did not affect cell proliferation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest, financial or otherwise.

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